

Chemical Constituents of *Ficus krishnae*

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Many plants of genus *Ficus* are used in medicine for the treatment of various ailments¹. Isolation of flavonoidal alkaloids ficine and isoficine² has accelerated the search of other potent components in *F. krishnae* which has not been investigated so far. We now report the isolation of atlantoflavone³ 8,8-dimethyl-5-hydroxy-2-(4'-hydroxyphenyl)-4*H*,8*H*-benzo[1,2-*b*:3,4-*b'*]pyran-4-one alongwith β -sitosterol and a mixture of olefinic long-chain hydrocarbons (C₃₀H₆₀ + C₃₂H₆₄ + C₃₄H₆₈) from this plant.

The dried leaves of *F. krishnae* (1 kg) (procured from A. M. U. Botanical Garden, Aligarh) were extracted with EtOH. The ethanol concentrated was treated with petrol and benzene respectively. The two extracts were combined and chromatographed over Si-gel column. Elution of the column with petrol, petrol-benzene and benzene afforded FK-1, FK-2 and FK-3 fractions.

FK-1 (60 mg) was crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH as white crystals (m.p. 80°) and characterised as a mixture of olefinic long-chain hydrocarbons (C₃₀H₆₀ + C₃₂H₆₄ + C₃₄H₆₈) on the basis of mass spectrum. FK-2 (120 mg) was crystallised from

CHCl₃-MeOH as white needles (m.p. 138°) and characterised as β -sitosterol by direct comparison with authentic sample (m.m.p., co-chromatography). FK-3 (100 mg) was crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH as yellow crystals (m.p. 287°) (the acetate, m.p. 224°) and identified as atlantoflavone on the basis of spectral (uv, ¹H nmr and MS) data.

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